

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/377926458>

Development of an e-Prescription Android Mobile application to Deliver the Primary Health Care Needs During COVID19 Lockdown in Sri Lanka

Conference Paper · January 2021

CITATIONS

0

READ

1

3 authors:

Prabath Tharanga Jayatissa

Post Doctoral Researcher at Ludwig Boltzmann Institute for Digital Health and Pr...

18 PUBLICATIONS 27 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Avanthi Rupasinghe

University of Colombo

4 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Anuradha Piyadasa

Institute of Archaeology and Heritage Studeis

4 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Development of an e-Prescription Android Mobile application to Deliver the Primary Health Care Needs During COVID19 Lockdown in Sri Lanka

Prabath Jayatissa¹, Avanthi Rupasinghe², Anuradha Piyadasa³

1. Post Graduate Institute of Medicine, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka

2. Post Graduate Institute of Medicine, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka

3. General Hospital Kalutara, Sri Lanka

Jayathissa.wgpt2015@pgim.cmb.ac.lk, avanthi319@gmail.com, anuradha@ieee.org

ABSTRACT

Introduction:

Among many of the e-Practices in the arena of Healthcare, an integral and efficient one is e-Prescription or Electronic Prescription Solution. It is certainly making healthcare immensely easier and smoother, and its endeavour to connect all of the patient's healthcare providers, thus it facilitates efficient and accurate decision-making. Moreover, Information technology has been crucial in influencing the world and the technology has not left the functioning of the healthcare industry untouched. Human interactive mobile application are developed without ethical consideration. This project focused on Development and implementation of e-Prescription Android Mobile application has facilitated the long due need for e-Prescription Android Mobile application of government health institutions in Sri Lanka with the consideration of Medical ethics.

Objectives:

General Objective:

- Developing an e-Prescription Android Mobile application.

Specific Objectives:

- Identify the key requirement of e-Prescription Android Mobile application.
- Identify the key aspect of the of medical ethics in the development of the mobile application.
- Developing the android application using android base MIT app inventor Platform and the web base programme using Php and MySQL.

Methods:

This project consisted of 3 phases. Phase 1: Ethical aspects and Requirement analysis and using focus group discussions (FGD) using online teleconferencing platform with general practisers and medical administrators. Phase 2: Identification of the suitable development

environment and web-based dashboard for the users. Phase 3: Development of the e-Prescription Android Mobile application.

Results:

FGD were conducted in 3 healthcare institutes. There were 31 interviewers (Male - 16, and female - 15) using the teleconferencing platform due to COVID19 lockdown. They highlighted the key requirements for the mobile application. Which were the teleconferencing feature, e-prescription system connectivity to pharmacy, Storage of data, patients confidentiality, avoid unauthorised access, unique verification, security of personal identifiable data. Linking with the personal health care number (PHN) through Master Patient Index (MPI) to anonymised the data to avoid ethical implication. Using this information, the requirements specification for mobile application was developed. The MIT app inventor and other web-based programming language(Php) and database language(MySQL) were used for the development. Mobile application prototype is developed and piloted in Kalutara District using several general practitioners..

Conclusions: Development and implementation of e-Prescription Android Mobile application has facilitated the long due need for e-Prescription Android Mobile application of health institutions in Sri Lanka.

KEYWORDS

MPI, PHN, e-Prescription, MIT App inventor, Telemedicine, Php, MySQL, Teleconferencing, Medical Ethics,